

THERAPEUTIC RECREATION CAN BE CONSIDER AS A SAFETY VALVE TO MINIMISE THE CYBER BULLYING DURING PANDEMIC

Dr. Rudra Prasad Saha*, Dr. Abantika Mondal, Dr. Biswajit Bala** & Dr. Kishore Mukhopadhyay*****

* Assistant Professor & HOD, Department of Education, Muralidhar Girls' College, Kolkata, West Bengal

** Assistant Professor, Department of Teacher Education, WBUTTEPA, Kolkata, West Bengal

*** Associate Professor, Department of Physical Education, Union Christian Training College, Berhampore, Murshidabad, West Bengal

Cite This Article: Dr. Rudra Prasad Saha, Dr. Abantika Mondal, Dr. Biswajit Bala & Dr. Kishore Mukhopadhyay, "Therapeutic Recreation can be Consider as a Safety Valve to Minimise the Cyber Bullying During Pandemic", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 6, Issue 2, Page Number 11-17, 2021.

Abstract:

The COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically changed the nature of trafficking. As schools were forced closure and switch to remote learning across most of the country of the world. All teaching-learning replaces largely through virtual mode. The student gets enough opportunity to use social media online for education and recreation, which in turn creates hazards for their mental health. Cyber bullying is a new phenomenon associated with children and young adults and this particular type of crime is increasing day by day. Active and therapeutic recreation is the only remedy to minimize cyber bullying in accordance with proper counseling. The present research article discussed the various aspects of cybercrime and the role of therapeutic recreation to reduce the rate of crime and improve the mental health of the victims.

Key Words: Therapeutic Recreation, Cyber Bullying and Pandemic.

Introduction:

For few decades, school-based bullying and cyber bullying have been the focus of policy and legal programs because of their profound impact on the physical and mental health of young people (1-2). Teens who are involved in bullying - as both victims and abusers - are more likely to experience depression (3), anxiety (4), suicidal thoughts and behavior (5) than their peers who are not involved. Cyber bullying also has a stronger effect on suicidal ideation than with peer pressure (6).

In December 2019, a collection of pneumonia cases was reported in Wuhan, China, later renamed Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 11 Feb 2020 (7). On 11 Mar 2020, the WHO announced that the epidemic had erupted (7) and that the economic recession was expected to lead to an increase in suicides and mental health related issues. Several researchers have reported an increase in depression in more people and people with existing psychiatric disorders, and health workers (8-10). Together, there is an urgent need to pay more attention to public mental health and policies to help people during this difficult time.

Extensive closures forced to respond to the ongoing outbreak of Covid-19 have prevented many people in their homes from leaving them to spend more time online. The new reality of living completely within the four walls has made the whole world more dependent on online platforms for communication, entertainment, work and education. People spend a lot of time on social media, chat rooms and sports services, and the problems that pervade these platforms - hatred, harassment, poisoning and bullying - have grown. Meanwhile, while today's kids and today's teens balance their social commitment between personal and online settings, they now only work online. Research reveals a disturbing rise in online toxicity and cyber bullying among children, especially when they are heavily dependent on digital platforms (11).

For many children and adolescents, the social isolation of the world during the global COVID-19 epidemic means that the contact is limited on virtually. As a result, they use social media and applications such as Tik Tok, Face Book, and Zoom more often than ever before. And while there are many good things that can come out of this online connection - like giving children important connections in the outside world - there are no risks. In fact, some of the biggest threats online to children are cyber bullying, shame and exploitation. In fact, initial research shows that cyber bullying increases during the home stay order.

According to Light, an organization that monitors online harassment and hate speech, there has been a 70% increase in cyber bullying in just a few months. They also found a 40% increase in toxicity on online gaming platforms, a 900% increase in hate speech on Twitter targeting China and China, and a 200% increase in traffic hate sites (11).

Recent technological advances have led to a progressive shift in the notion of human relations. Voluntary access to social networking and online communities means immediate web-mediated access (12). This transformation in human relationships took place very quickly and mainly involved younger generations (13). Parents, teachers and adults are not always aware of the functioning, rules, or dangers of the web and are

often exposed to acts of violence and harassment among their peers, which can have serious and far-reaching consequences.

Cyber bullying is one of the known risks of this technological change and contains voluntary and repetitive actions against one or more individuals, through computers and technology (14). Cyber bullying is characterized by the following: voluntary, deliberate and unintentional behavior; repetitive action, behavior is repeated over time and is not reduced to a single event; to see the damage done, the victim experiences the damage done; the use of electronic devices, cyber bullying is carried out using computers, cell phones, and other electronic means. Cyber bullying, like common bullying, is based on an equal power relationship used by a cyber bully against the victim (15). A key feature of cyber bullying is web-based anonymity, which evokes the perception of vulnerability and loneliness for victims (16). Peer segregation, low self-esteem, and social anxiety are the most common consequences for cyber victims.

The COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically changed the nature of trafficking. As schools were forced closure and switch to remote learning across the U.S. by March 2020, there has been a sudden decline in humanity communication and amazing emergence in the use of digital technology (17-18).

With this change came public concern over the consequences of increasing children's dependence on technology, including the potential for greater exposure to cyber bullying (19). Indeed, some research before COVID-19 has shown that high frequency of internet use is associated with an increase in youth reports of cybercrime and cyber victimization (20). Thus, the media set out the expectations that while domestic exploitation has declined, cyber bullying may increase. This disruption in the traditional functioning of schools it provides an opportunity to test the reunion of abusers as well cyber bullying and personal learning.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has described bullying as a major public health problem. It can result in depression, anxiety and sometimes suicide. It can also lead to substance abuse, social withdrawal, missing school or dropping out, and can have implications later in life, according to the WHO (21).

The reduction in bullying, even in regions that offer personal learning, may explain the mixed results among early studies on the influence of COVID-19 on adolescent mental health. The decline caused by the epidemic in abuse may have negative consequences for the child in mental health issues. The initial concern is that the epidemic will seriously damage the mental health of students (22) was slightly supported but not fully supported by the following data which raises controversy, a small increase in such measures (23-24). Other studies have suggested that a small portion of young people define their mental health as progress during school closure (25). Forced peer pressure may be helpful to those who will attend victims, or even perpetrators (26).

The present article discussed critically the impact of pandemic on cyber bullying and the role of positive recreation to minimize the cause and effect of cyber bullying.

What is Cyber Bullying?

Bullying implies an intention to harm, intimidate or coerce an act when there is an imbalance of power and the act is a cause for distress and provocation. Bullying may be verbal, physical or mental in nature and a whole spectrum of acts can constitute bullying (27).

Cyber bullying is bullying with the use of digital technologies. It can take place on social media, messaging platforms, gaming platforms and mobile phones. It is repeated behaviour, aimed at scaring, angering or shaming those who are targeted.

For instances,

- Spreading lies about or posting embarrassing photos of someone on social media
- Sending hurtful messages or threats via messaging platforms
- Impersonating someone and sending mean messages to others on their behalf.
- Face-to-face bullying and cyber bullying can often happen alongside each other. But cyber bullying leaves a digital footprint – a record that can prove useful and provide evidence to help stop the abuse (28).

Parents, caregivers and educators should be on alert for behavior changes and other signs that a child is being bullied, the symptoms may be as follows, (29).

Facts about Bullying:

- Bullying is unwanted, aggressive behavior among school-aged children that involves a real or perceived power imbalance. The behavior is repeated, or has the potential to be repeated, over time. Bullying includes actions such as making threats, spreading rumors, attacking someone physically or verbally, and excluding someone from a group on purpose. Bullying can occur in-person or through technology.
- Bullying has serious and lasting negative effects on the mental health and overall well-being of youth involved in bullying in any way including: those who bully others, youth who are bullied, as well as those youth who both bully others and are bullied by others, sometimes referred to as bully-victims.
- Even youth who have observed but not participated in bullying behavior report significantly more feelings of helplessness and less sense of connectedness and support from responsible adults (parents/schools) than youth who have not witnessed bullying behavior.

- Negative outcomes of bullying (for youth who bully others, youth who are bullied, and youth who both are bullied and bully others) may include: depression, anxiety, involvement in interpersonal violence or sexual violence, substance abuse, poor social functioning, and poor school performance, including lower grade point averages, standardized test scores, and poor attendance.
- Youth who report frequently bullying others and youth who report being frequently bullied are at increased risk for suicide-related behavior.
- Youth who report both bullying others and being bullied (bully-victims) have the highest risk for suicide-related behavior of any groups that report involvement in bullying (<https://www.cdc.gov/violenceprevention/pdf/bullying-suicide-translation-final-a.pdf>).

Signs of Cyber Bullying:

- A decline in grades
- Unexplainable injuries
- Depression
- A change in eating habits and sleep patterns
- Feelings of helplessness or decreased self esteem
- Increased physical complaints (headaches, stomach upset, etc)
- School avoidance (When kids are in the classroom, 5.4 million students want to stay home every day or fear of being bullied.)
- Kids and teens experience self-destructive behaviors such as running away from home, self-harm or talking about suicide.

Types of Cyber Bullying:

October is National Bullying Prevention Month, and schools across the United States are standing up against bullying, and educating on prevention (30).

- **Isolation or Exclusion:** Dismissal is the act of deliberately leaving someone out. Releases exist in cases of human abuse, but are also used online to identify and harass the victim. If someone excluded from social media group without valid reason it is a matter of prestige and humiliation. The group admin is sole responsible for that.
- **Abuse:** Harassment is a broad category in which many forms of cybercrime fall under it, but it usually refers to a continuous pattern of harmful online or threatening online messages sent with the intent to harm someone.
- **Travel / Doxing:** Withdrawal, also known as doxing, means the act of disclosing sensitive or personal information to someone without his or her consent in order to humiliate embarrassing individual. This can range from the distribution of personal photos or social media documents to the sharing of personal messages stored in a private online group. What is important is the lack of consent for the victim.
- **Deception:** Cheating is like going out, with something more deceptive. In such a case, the bully will be the friend, and the victim will have a false sense of security. Once the bully has gained their trust, they abuse that trust and share the victim's secrets and confidential information with a third party or with a third party.
- **Cyber Stalking:** Cyber stalking is a very serious form of cyber bullying that can lead to threats of physical harm to a target child. It can include surveillance, false accusations, threats, and is often accompanied by offline tracking. It is a criminal offense and can lead to deterrence, court proceedings, and imprisonment.
- **Explosion:** Filtering is when a bully uses social media accounts with your child to send inappropriate content with his or her name. It can be dangerous when friends write funny posts on each other's profiles, but it has the potential to be incredibly dangerous. For example, a bully sends racist / homosexual profanity through another person's profile to tarnish his or her reputation.
- **Imitation:** Hypocrisy occurs when a bully creates an online profile or identity online for the sole purpose of harassing someone online. This may include creating a false email account, a fake social media profile, and choosing new identities and photos to deceive the victim. In these cases, the bully is more likely to be a well-informed victim.
- **Disposal:** Dismissal refers to an act of bullying that spreads aggressive information about their intentions through public sending or confidential messages to tarnish their image or relationships. In these cases, the bully usually has a personal relationship with the victim, either as an acquaintance or as a friend.
- **Tramplng:** Trolling is when a bully will want to deliberately annoy others by posting hot comments online. Trolling may not always be a form of cyber bullying, but it can be used as a tool for cyber bullying when it is used with malicious and malicious intent. These bullies are often severely isolated from their victims, and have no personal relationships.

- **Burning Flames:** This type of cyber bullying involves sending or sending direct profanity and slander to those who are targeted. Burning is like trampling, but it will usually be a direct attack on the victim to motivate them in online battles.

Cyber Bullying Behaviour Might Include:

- Abusive texts and emails
- Hurtful messages, images or videos
- Imitating others online
- Excluding others online
- Humiliating others online
- Spreading nasty online gossip and chat
- Creating fake accounts to trick someone or humiliate them (31).
- Shairing edited unwanted photograph etc;

Effects of Covid Pandemic on Cyber Bullying:

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to an increase in kids and teens using digital platforms, not just for personal use, but for education purposes as well. For many young people, social distancing guidelines mean the only contact they will have with their peers will be done virtually. As a result, young people are using social platforms like TikTok, Zoom and others more frequently than in the past. While there are benefits that can result from online interactions, like connecting kids to the outside world, it doesn't eliminate the risks.

With social distancing firmly in place and the vast majority of schools teaching remotely, it stands to reason that kids are going to be online now more than ever. After all, their education is pretty much dependent on the Internet.

Teachers are using programs like Google Classroom, Moodle, Zoom, Canvas, Web-Ex, and Blackboard. Some are even using Roblox, Twitch, Minecraft, and YouTube. Consequently, students are stuck at home and being forced to use online platforms for learning. In addition to the increasing use of technology, there are other factors that contribute to this increase:

- **Increased Stress:** The epidemic has become very stressful and confusing for everyone. Often when children feel stressed or confused, it leads to work or bullying others, arguments between friends and behavior that jeopardizes responding.
- **Isolation:** Compulsory stay-at-home orders can create feelings of loneliness, which can lead to broken relationships. Some children may have limited access to the Internet, which may make them feel more isolated. Over and over again, they can make rude or cruel comments in frustration, especially when they feel that they have lost touch with their group of friends.
- **Decreased Online Guidance:** As more and more parents try to balance homework, helping with homework and managing the new world, they are less likely to pay close attention to what their children are doing online.
- **Loneliness:** Sometimes children engage in cyber bullying because they are bored, lonely or want attention. Because the epidemic worsens these problems, it can lead to online behavior. Some children bully to relieve stress, but also because they are bored.

To make matters worse, many networks that support victims of violence have been shut down. In some cases, counselors are inaccessible, and face-to-face discussions with teachers and coaches are also limited. Many children are not accustomed to talking to their parents about what is happening, as they may worry that their use of technology will be limited, which is currently their only connection to friends (32-33).

Therapeutic Recreation:

According to the American Therapeutic Recreation Association (ATRA), recreational therapy or therapeutic recreation (TR) is a systematic process that utilizes recreation (leisure) and other activities as interventions to address the assessed needs of individuals with illnesses and/or disabling conditions, as a means to psychological and physical health, recovery and well-being. Recreational therapy may also be simply referred to as recreation therapy; in short it is the utilization and enhancement of leisure (34).

The work of recreational therapists differ from other professionals on the basis of using leisure activities alone to meet well-being goals, they work with clients to enhance motor, social and cognitive functioning, build confidence, develop coping skills, and integrate skills learned in treatment settings into community settings. Intervention areas vary widely and are based upon enjoyable and rewarding interests of the client. Examples of intervention modalities include creative arts (e.g., crafts, music, dance, drama, among others), games, sports like adventure programming, exercises like dance/movement, and skill enhancement activities (Motor, locomotion, sensory, cognition, communication, and behavior).

Recreation and Leisure:

Recreation and leisure have been incorporated into the lives of individuals across cultures and throughout history. Commonly interchangeable terms, the two are both focused on providing participants with experiences. The drive and motivation behind each experience is what differentiates the kind of leisure and/or

recreation occurring. For example, leisure may be viewed with respect to time, activity, or state of mind. Leisure as time indicates that leisure is understood to be time that is unrestricted by other experiences, such as work, tasks, or obligations. Leisure as activity is viewed as the activities chosen to participate in when one engages in free time. Leisure as a state of mind signifies the participants' internal experience of self, which involves the previously discussed topics of perceived freedom, intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, and self-determination, among many other internal states (35).

Recreation is similar to leisure. According to Anderson and Hurd (2011), "recreation is an activity that people engage in during their free time, that people enjoy, and that people recognize as having socially redeeming values". Recreation differs from leisure in that it has a connection with social values and recognition; the activity an individual participates in must be morally acceptable to the public and viewed in some way as valuable. Because of this, recreation may change greatly depending on history and culture.

Adapting Therapeutic Recreation:

There are many ways to bring joy and meaning to daily living, even while social distancing, and even without the physical space of the activity room hub.

Below is a list of activities that have been available to Community Health Care Centre's (CHCC) long-term care residents during the COVID-19 pandemic (36),

- Technology use has increased; video chats with family members and other loved ones have become very popular,
- A printed activity packet – which includes puzzles, jokes, a hymn, a daily devotional and "Today in History" information – is distributed each weekday and once on the weekend. This is a new offering that, based on popularity, will most likely continue long after COVID-19 is gone.
- CHCC's courtyard garden is open so staff can take residents out for a bit of fresh air and sunshine. Thank you to the generous people who donated extra flowers for the garden this year!
- There are daily opportunities for one-on-one interactions with CHCC staff, which often include board games, manicures, writing cards and letters, reading aloud, and sharing books and magazines.
- Portable DVD players are available for those who would like to watch a movie in their rooms. Again, thank you to the community members who donated fresh movies for our residents!
- Audio books, headphones and CD players are available on demand.
- iPads are available for those who would like to watch YouTube videos featuring animals, nature, travel and more.
- Increment of TV viewing time specially sporting and adventure activities,
- In room dance, yoga practices can be administered,
- App based physical activities programmes are popularized nowadays,
- Encourage the participation of online live interactive programmes.
- Recreation therapy moves into a virtual reality: Between isolation, lockdowns, and physical distancing, much of the world has been forced to go virtual for all things business and social, and West Park Healthcare Centre has been no different. Delivering patient care has no doubt changed with more personal protective equipment required, more infection prevention and control measures, and more risk. But a sometimes-overlooked but integral part of patient care has had to adapt to a new, digital world (37).

Domain of Therapeutic Recreation:

The domain of Therapeutic recreation includes the following (36),

Importance Recreational Therapy:

Recreational therapy has wide-ranging positive impacts on your physical and mental health. This is especially the case when the therapy is designed around your individual interests and needs.

Let's dive into some of the science-backed benefits of these therapies.

- **Improves Symptoms of Depression:** Many therapeutic recreation programs get people up and moving and stimulating their minds with engaging, creative tasks. Music therapy, art therapy, drama, and dance also all have positive effects on depression symptoms. Researchers believe the improvement may be linked to endorphins. These feel-good chemicals are released in your brain during physical movement, when you express yourself creatively, and during social interactions.
- **Increases Self-Esteem:** Research shows that recreational therapy may help improve a person's self-confidence and self-esteem. After a structured program where the adults engaged in their chosen activities every week and did simple upper body exercises, they reported improved self-esteem compared with how they felt before starting the therapy program.
- **Strengthens Social Connections:** Illness, injury, and disability can limit your ability to interact with people. Recreational therapy provides opportunities to engage with other people in positive ways, which can counteract feelings of isolation. Stronger social bonds like these are associated with better health outcomes across the board.
- **Improves Functional Independence:** After an Injury: In many cases, a serious injury can affect your ability to do routine tasks. Taking care of your home, exercising, playing with your children or grandchildren — these activities may be difficult or impossible after an injury. Recreational therapy for people with injuries is also associated with more social activity, greater involvement with sports or aquatic activities, and fewer pressure ulcers.
- **Increases Strength and Physical Fitness:** Recreational therapy often includes exercise, games, dance, yoga, tai chi, and other kinds which are able to increase strength, flexibility, agility and other components of physical fitness.
- **Boosts Cognitive Abilities:** Physical exercise, social engagement, and games that stimulate brain (such as bridge, chess, and memory challenges) all improve the healthy functioning of mind. It's important to bear in mind that recreational therapy can't fully restore areas of the brain that have been permanently damaged. Physical activity, social relationships, and activities that challenge your thinking may all help maintain the healthy functioning of your **brain**.
- **Relieves Anxiety for Children Who Are Hospitalized:** Being treated in a hospital is a stressful, fearful experience for a child. recreational therapy in a pediatric hospital may help reduce those negative feelings. This can be particularly important if a child visits hospitals repeatedly due to a chronic condition. It build good relationship between the patient and health care workers (39).

Conclusion:

Keeping the view of global pandemic where are three time increase in mental health related issues globally, especially children and young adults. According to WHO inactivity is the fourth leading cause of death and the rate of suicide is enormous now a days. In the pandemic all the educational institutions are almost closed and 184 countries declared work from home. The students are not getting enough scope to intermix with friends and forced to depend on online learning. The screen viewing time increased significantly which results some negative impact on their mind. Cyber bullying nowadays a new type of crime based on social media. Therapeutic recreation plays a vital role to minimize the rate of cyber crime and promote mental health. Indoor recreational activities with family members, free hand exercise, yogic practices, engage minor games and gramification is highly recommended during the pandemic for the children and young adults.

References:

1. Holt, M. K., A. M. Vivolo-Kantor, J. R. Polanin, K. M. Holland, S. DeGue, J. L. Matjasko, M. Wolfe, and G. Reid (2015). Bullying and suicidal ideation and behaviors: a meta-analysis. *Pediatrics* 135(2), e496–e509.
2. Wolke, D., W. E. Copeland, A. Angold, and E. J. Costello (2013). Impact of bullying in childhood on adult health, wealth, crime, and social outcomes. *Psychological science* 24(10), 1958–1970.
3. Wang, J., T. R. Nansel, and R. J. Iannotti (2011). Cyber and traditional bullying: Differential association with depression. *Journal of adolescent health* 48(4), 415–417.
4. Kowalski, R. M. and S. P. Limber (2013). Psychological, physical, and academic correlates of cyberbullying and traditional bullying. *Journal of adolescent health* 53(1), S13–S20.
5. Holt, M. K., A. M. Vivolo-Kantor, J. R. Polanin, K. M. Holland, S. DeGue, J. L. Matjasko, M. Wolfe, and G. Reid (2015). Bullying and suicidal ideation and bhaviors: a meta-analysis. *Pediatrics* 135(2), e496– e509.
6. Van Geel, M., P. Vedder, and J. Tanilon (2014). Relationship between peer victimization, cyber bullying, and suicide in children and adolescents: a meta-analysis. *JAMA pediatrics* 168(5), 435–442.
7. Anand, K.B., Karade, S., Sen, S., Gupta, R.M., 2020. SARS-CoV-2: camazotz's curse. *Med.J. Armed Forces India* 76, 136–141.
8. Hao, F., Tan, W., Jiang, L., Zhang, L., Zhao, X., Zou, Y., Hu, Y., Luo, X., Jiang, X., McIntyre, R.S., Tran, B., Sun, J., Zhang, Z., Ho, R., Ho, C., Tam, W., 2020. Do psychiatric patients experience more

- psychiatric symptoms during COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown? A case-control study with service and research implications for immunopsychiatry. *Brain Behav. Immun.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2020.04.069>
9. Tan, W., Hao, F., McIntyre, R.S., Jiang, L., Jiang, X., Zhang, L., Zhao, X., Zou, Y., Hu, Y., Luo, X., Zhang, Z., Lai, A., Ho, R., Tran, B., Ho, C., Tam, W., 2020. Is returning to work during the COVID-19 pandemic stressful? A study on immediate mental health status and psychoneuroimmunity prevention measures of Chinese workforce. *Brain Behav. Immun.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2020.04.055>.
 10. Wang, Y., Di, Y., Ye, J., Wei, W., 2020b. Study on the public psychological states and its related factors during the outbreak of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in some regions of China. *Psychol. Health Med.* 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2020.1746817>.
 11. https://11ght.com/Toxicity_during_coronavirus_Report-L1ght.pdf
 12. Auriemma, V., Iorio, G., Roberti, G., and Morese, R. (2020). Cyber bullying and empathy in the Ahe of hyper connection: an interdisciplinary approach. *Front. Sociol.* 5, 1–11.
 13. Eleuteri, S., Saladino, V., and Verrastro, V. (2017). Identity, relationships, sexuality, and risky behaviors of adolescents in the context of social media. *Sex. Relationsh. Ther.* 32, 354–365.
 14. Aboujaoude, E., Savage, M. W., Starcevic, V., and Salame, W. O. (2015). Cyber bullying: review of an old problem gone viral. *J. Adoles. Health* 57, 10–18.
 15. Durak, Y. H., and Saritepeci, M. (2020). Examination of the relationship between cyber bullying and cyber victimization. *J. Child Fam. Stud.* 29, 2905–2915
 16. Cao, W., Fang, Z., Hou, G., Han, M., Xu, X., Dong, J., et al. (2020). The psychological impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on college students in China.
 17. Koeze, E. and N. Popper (2020, April 7). The virus changed the way we internet. *The New York Times*.
 18. De, R., N. Pandey, and A. Pal (2020). Impact of digital surge during Covid-19 pandemic: A viewpoint on research and practice. *International Journal of Information Management* 55, 102171.
 19. Sparks, S. (2020, July 22). Cyber bullying, mental health, and other school-safety takeaways for school reopening. *Education Week*.
 20. Kowalski, R. M., S. P. Limber, and A. McCord (2019). A developmental approach to cyber bullying: Prevalence and protective factors. *Aggression and Violent Behavior* 45, 20–32.
 21. <https://www.mibluesperspectives.com/2020/10/12/increase-in-cyberbullying-during-covid-19/>
 22. <https://www.verywellfamily.com/cyberbullying-increasing-during-global-pandemic-4845901>
 23. Golberstein, E., H. Wen, and B. F. Miller (2020, 09). Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) and Mental Health for Children and Adolescents. *JAMA Pediatrics* 174(9), 819–820.
 24. Kemper, A. R., C. A. Hostutler, K. Beck, C. A. Fontanella, and J. A. Bridge (2021). Depression and suiciderisk screening results in pediatric primary care. *Pediatrics.* 12
 25. Leeb, R. T., R. H. Bitsko, L. Radhakrishnan, P. Martinez, R. Njai, and K. M. Holland (2020). Mental health-related emergency department visits among children aged; 18 years during the covid-19 pandemic-united states, january 1–october 17, 2020. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report* 69(45), 1675.
 26. Ford, T., A. John, and D. Gunnell (2021). Mental health of children and young people during pandemic. *BMJ (Clinical Research ed.)* 372, n614–n614.
 27. Diva Rai , Anti-Bullying Laws in India, 2019, <https://blog.ipleaders.in/bullying/>
 28. <https://www.unicef.org/end-violence/how-to-stop-cyberbullying>
 29. <https://www.stompoutbullying.org/blog/Cyberbullying-During-COVID-19>
 30. <https://blog.securly.com/2018/10/04/the-10-types-of-cyberbullying/>
 31. <https://www.esafety.gov.au/key-issues/cyberbullying>
 32. <https://www.mibluesperspectives.com/2020/10/12/increase-in-cyberbullying-during-covid-19/>
 33. <https://www.verywellfamily.com/cyberbullying-increasing-during-global-pandemic-4845901>
 34. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Recreational_therapy
 35. Anderson, D., & Hurd, A. (2011). Introduction and overview. In Kassing, G., Vallese, R., Cole, A., & Campbell, D. (Eds.), *The park and recreation professional’s handbook* (pp. 1-15). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
 36. <https://growthroughflow.com/5-ways-recreation-therapy-can-improve-your-life/>
 37. http://www.jgypk.hu/tamop15e/tananyag_html/Rekreacio_I_angol/i3_the_classification_of_movement_s_recreation.html
 38. <https://www.oha.com/news/recreation-therapy-moves-into-a-virtual-reality>
 39. Mukhopadhyay, K,(2021) Role of Therapeutic Recreation in the Covid19 Pandemic, *Praxis International Journal of Social Science and Literature, (PIJSSL), Volume - 4, Issue - 4, April – 2021*